

INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES FOR THE PROCESSING OF RAW MATERIALS OF PLANT ORIGIN TO IMPROVE THE QUALITY OF FOOD SUPPLY OF THE TROOPS

Mykola Riabchykov¹, Iryna Tsykhanovska², Lidiia Tovma³, Oleksandr Aleksandrov⁴, Denis Kovylev⁵, Oleh Rikunov⁶, Oleh Smahin⁷, Kostiantyn Orlov⁸

¹Department of Light Industry, Lutsk National Technical University, Lutsk, Ukraine
ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9382-7562>

²Department of Food Technology, Light Industry and Design, Ukrainian Engineering-Pedagogics Academy, Kharkiv, Ukraine
ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9713-9257>

³Department of Technical and Logistic Support, National Academy of National Guard of Ukraine, Kharkiv, Ukraine
ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5074-8303>

⁴Department of Food Technology, Light Industry and Design, Ukrainian Engineering-Pedagogics Academy, Kharkiv, Ukraine
ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3592-285X>

⁵Department of Food Technology, Light Industry and Design, Ukrainian Engineering-Pedagogics Academy, Kharkiv, Ukraine

⁶Department of Operational and Logistics Support, National Academy of National Guard of Ukraine, Kharkiv, Ukraine
ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7581-7531>

⁷Department of Technical and Logistical Support, National Academy of National Guard of Ukraine, Kharkiv, Ukraine
ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2974-8368>

⁸National Academy of National Guard of Ukraine, Kharkiv, Ukraine
✉Corresponding author: Lidiia Tovma, e-mail: l.f.tovma@gmail.com

ARTICLE INFO

Article history:

Received date 06.09.2022

Accepted date 22.10.2022

Published date 30.10.2022

Section:

Food production

DOI

10.21303/2313-8416.2022.002772

KEY WORDS

Flaxseeds
Nanoparticles (NPs FeO×Fe₂O₃ – nanomagnetite)
Bacteriostatic (protective) properties
food supply
servicemen

ABSTRACT

The object of research: morphological and cultural characteristics of micromycetes: yeast *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* and mycelial fungi *Mucor racemosus* grown on agar medium.

The subject of research: flax seed suspension, ultrafine powder of double oxide of divalent and trivalent ferrum, micromycetes: yeast *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* and mycelial fungi *Mucor racemosus*

Investigated problem: ensuring the bacteriostatic properties of raw materials and obtaining products with an extended dates of expiry.

The subject in scientific results: the impact of nanoparticles (NP FeO×Fe₂O₃) on the bacteriostatic (protective) properties of flax seeds against fungal infections has been studied and the dependence of bacteriostatic properties on the amount of nanomagnetite has been determined. The ability of nanomagnetite to improve the bacteriostatic properties of flax seeds has been proven: addition of 0.1 %; 0.15 %; 0.2 % of nanomagnetite suppresses the development of microflora (micromycetes) in flax seed samples by 8–20 times. A reduction in the number of micromycetes (yeast *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* and mycelial fungi *Mucor racemosus*) by 8–10 times and the size by 10–20 times was established compared to the control. The rational content of nanoparticles (NPs FeO×Fe₂O₃–nanomagnetite) has been determined as 0.15 % of the weight of the recipe mixture.

The proposed mathematical model makes it possible to predict the effectiveness of using NP FeO×Fe₂O₃ – nanomagnetite to inhibit the growth of mycelial fungi to ensure the bacteriostatic properties of raw materials, in particular, flax seeds.

The area of practical use of the research results: food industry enterprises specializing in the production of bakery and flour confectionery products using a mixture of wheat and rye flour with the addition of food additives.

Innovative technological product: flour raw material with a mineral nano-additive suspension based on the double oxide of divalent and trivalent ferrum, which allows to ensure quality and extend dates of expiry of the product.

Scope of the innovative technological product: to enhance the quality of food supply of the troops in extreme conditions.

© The Author(s) 2021. This is an open access article under the Creative Commons CC BY license

Riabchykov, M., Tsykhanovska, I., Tovma, L., Aleksandrov, O., Kovylev, D., Rikunov, O., Smahin, O., Orlov, K. (2022). Innovative technologies for the processing of raw materials of plant origin to improve the quality of food supply of the troops. *ScienceRise*, 5, 21–29. doi: <http://doi.org/10.21303/2313-8416.2022.002772>

1. Introduction

The effect of nanoparticles (NPs) of double divalent and trivalent iron oxide (FeO×Fe₂O₃ – nanomagnetite) on protection of flax seeds against fungal infections was studied, and the dependence of this effect on the amount of nanomagnetite nanoparticles was determined.

1. 1. The object of research

Object of research: morphological and cultural characteristics of micromycetes: yeast *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* and mycelialfungi *Mucor racemosus*, grown on an agar medium.

Subject of research: flax seed suspension, ultrafine powder of double oxide of divalent and trivalent ferrum, micromycetes: yeast *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* and mycelial fungi *Mucor racemosus*.

1. 2. Problem description

The main problems in the storage of flax seed, especially if it is related to food products for health [1] consumer properties [2] is to ensure product quality. In particular, the article [3] describes special methods for determining flax seed quality indicators, including those related to damage, but the latter problem is not sufficiently developed.

A recognized problem in the preservation of flax seeds and the manufacture of products from it are their diseases and other negative factors [4], which significantly affect the nutritional properties [5]. This problem is described, but real ways of solving it are not defined. At the same time both negative food, and toxic properties can be shown [6, 7]. Unfortunately, the undeniable harmfulness of flax seeds diseases is not considered in terms of creating bacteriostatic storage conditions.

The norms of damage and contamination of flax seeds are also considered in [8, 9]. Different ways of solving the problem were considered at the stage when the danger has already been identified. In our opinion, the direction of creating conditions for inhibiting flax seeds diseases at the initial stages is more promising.

Analysis of studies on flax damage and problems has been linked to fungal infections, such as imperfect fungi *Colletotrichum lini* Mannset Bolley, *Fusarium oxysporum* Schl. f. line Bilai [10]. Some fungal infections of flax, as well as methods of control them are discussed in [11]. It should be noted that in most cases, these problems are solved when they have already arisen. It would be desirable to invent tools that would prevent adverse events.

The article [12] identifies fungal infections characteristic of seeds in general. It is desirable to develop practical methods of solving individual problems. The article [13] proposes active methods of combating flax diseases. We propose the creation of preventive methods that act at the initial stages of the occurrence of diseases.

Recent advances in plant and food protection have often been linked to nanotechnology and nanomaterials [13]. In particular, the effect of iron oxides is considered positive [14]. These studies considered the bacteriostatic properties of nanomaterials for dairy products subject to fungal infections. Considering the research data on the danger of contamination of flax seeds with fungal infections, we consider it relevant to check the effect on these products. Article [15] describes the use of magnetite nanoparticles in the food industry to increase bactericidal and bacteriostatic properties. These results make it possible to predict a positive effect in the protection of flax seeds. We would like to emphasize the bacteriostatic properties that allow to create preventive conditions for the fight against flax seeds.

1. 3. Suggested solution to the problem

Analysis of publications on flax seeds diseases showed the following:

1. The main problem for flax seeds is fungal infections, the effectiveness of combating them remains low.

2. Methods of combating fungal infections involve the treatment of infected products, it is desirable to develop preventive methods that include, in particular, the creation of bacteriostatic properties.

3. Preliminary studies of magnetic nanomaterials testify to their potential bacteriostatic properties. It is desirable to investigate these properties before fungal infections characteristic of flax seeds.

The aim of this work is to investigate the effect of magnetite nanoparticles on the resistance of flax seeds to fungal diseases at the stage of their development.

2. Materials and methods

Mycelial fungi (micromycetes) are a numerous and unique group of eukaryotic microorganisms, that have microscopic spore-forming structures such as mold, mildew, rust. The stench

does not take revenge on chlorophyll, not ready for the synthesis of organic substances from CO₂, which will require ready-made organic substances for development. Many types of micromycetes are harmless, exist, for example, as soil saprotrophs (reducers, saprophytes). Since saprotrophs cannot produce the compounds they need on their own, they are considered a type of heterotroph. They include many fungi (the rest are parasitic, mutualistic or commensalistic symbionts), bacteria and protozoa. Many thousands of species of micromycetes are found in lichens, forming symbiotic relationships with algae. Other micromycetes, such as members of the genera *Penicillium*, *Aspergillus*, and *Neurospora*, were first discovered as molds that cause spoilage of fruit and bread [16, 17].

Numerous fungi that grow on grains, industrial materials and viruses cause their effects and destruction. There are fungi that infect cultivated plants during their growing season, causing great damage to agriculture, as well as fungi that are pathogenic to humans and animals.

The method of determining harmful fungi is based on seeding the product or product homogenate and (or) their dilutions in nutrient media, determining the affiliation of isolated microorganisms to fungi by the characteristic growth on nutrient media and cell morphology.

The method is designed to: establish the compliance of microbiological indicators of food quality to the requirements of regulatory and technical documentation, to clarify the causes of product defects [16, 17].

Sowings of the product or its corresponding dilutions are carried out on Petri dishes, spend two parallel determinations. At the bottom of a sterile Petri dish make 1 cm³ of product or its dilution and sterile pour 15–20 cm³ of nutrient medium Saburo, or agar medium to identify harmful fungi. Petri dishes with crops are placed to solidify on a horizontal surface. then the Petri dishes are turned upside down and placed in a thermostat with a temperature of (24±1) °C for 5 days or at a temperature of (30±1) °C for 3–5 days. The crops are incubated at a temperature of (24±1) °C for 5 days, the crops on Petri dishes are thermostated upside down [16, 17].

After 3 days of thermostating, a preliminary count of typical colonies or the appearance of characteristic signs of growth on liquid nutrient media.

If in crops on dense media there are flour, very fast-growing fungi, the removal of preliminary results should be carried out very carefully, not allowing the spores of these fungi to crumble and give rise to secondary colonies. In 5 days the final account of results of thermostating of crops is carried out. Mushroom colonies are divided visually.

Colonies of fungi on flax seeds are shown in **Fig. 1**

Fig. 1. Colonies of fungi on flax seeds

The development of harmful fungi on nutrient media is accompanied by the appearance of mycelia of different colors.

For quantitative counting, cups are selected on which 5 to 50 colonies of harmful fungi have grown.

If it is necessary, microscopic studies are carried out to separate colonies of harmful fungi. For this aim, preparations are prepared from individual colonies or from cultures on a liquid medi-

um using the crushed drop method. A drop of sterile tap water is applied to the slide. Then a part of the colony is introduced into this drop with a heated needle or a drop of culture liquid is applied with a loop. The resulting suspension is covered with a cover glass.

Microscopy results are evaluated using the characteristics of harmful fungi.

If the growth of harmful fungi is detected when testing the product on nutrient media and their presence is confirmed by microscopy, then a conclusion is drawn about the presence of these microorganisms in the product.

Each cup is placed upside down and counted using a magnifying glass to count the number of colonies that have grown, counting the colonies of harmful fungi separately. Each counted colony is marked at the bottom of the cup.

The following method of counting the number of harmful fungi colonies is proposed in the work.

In the graphic editor, a circle is created, the diameter of which is equal to the real diameter of the Petri dish (95 mm) and a system of squares with a size of 1×1 mm. Rows of squares are placed in mutually perpendicular directions.

The photo of the drug is placed on the same sheet, its size is adapted to the size of the circle. A system of squares is superimposed on top (Fig. 2).

The number of colonies of harmful fungi is counted separately in each square. The number of colonies is recalculated according to the proportionality of the area of the circle and the area of the squares:

$$N_p = \frac{n\pi r^2}{x},$$

n – number of colonies counted in all squares;

r – the radius of the Petri dish;

x – the number of squares in which the calculation was carried out (in our case, 13).

For convenience when counting, it is possible to increase or decrease the size of the image.

The number of harmful fungi N , Q/g of product was calculated according to the formula:

$$N = \frac{N_p}{m} 10^p,$$

where m is the weight of the sample taken for sowing;

p is the number of 10-fold dilutions.

Fig. 2. Example of calculation of number of colonies in graphic editor

If the test of the product on nutrient media revealed the growth of fungi and their presence is confirmed by microscopy, it is concluded that the presence of these microorganisms in the product.

It is possible to slow down the development of the microflora and, accordingly, to extend the shelf life of the product by introducing additives that have a bacteriostatic effect into the product.

We offer as this additive a nanomaterial in the form of double oxide of ferrous and trivalent iron (NPs $\text{FeO}\times\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3$), described in our previous works [15, 18, 19].

To determine the properties of the environment where the fungi grew, nanomagnetite powder (NPs $\text{FeO}\times\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3$) was added to the flax seeds.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Determination of the effect of magnetite nanoparticles on the growth of harmful fungi

The main component of magnetite is nanoparticles of mixed oxide of divalent and trivalent iron with the general formula Fe_3O_4 or $\text{FeO}\times\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ with a nanoparticle size of 30–78 nm.

Nano-objects, which include nanomagnetite (NPs $\text{FeO}\times\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3$), have enormous potential and carry many important fundamental discoveries, new functional and technological properties and promising technological applications. It should be noted that most nanomaterials used in food products occupy an intermediate position between nano- and microstructures. Thus, the diameter of DNA is 12 nm, liposomes 30–10000 nm, amylopectin 44–200 nm, cubosomes 500 nm, nano-sensors < 1000 nm [18].

Nanoparticles of the multifunctional food additive of complex action magnetite (NPs $\text{FeO}\times\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3$) have a huge potential and high bioaffinity to biopolymers, in particular, proteins, carbohydrates. Therefore, they carry many important fundamental discoveries, new functional and technological properties and promising technological applications. Noncovalent adsorption of polymer molecules, H_2O dipoles occurs on the surface of magnetic nanoparticles (NPs $\text{FeO}\times\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3$). The process of adsorption of biopolymeric food ingredients and water is mainly determined by ionic, van der Waals, hydrogen and hydrophobic types of interactions. These interactions occur between the surface of nanoparticles (NPs $\text{FeO}\times\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3$) and adsorbing molecules and entail a change in the Gibbs free energy. The result is the formation of supramolecular ensembles, which significantly affect the functional and technological properties of raw components and semi-finished products, as well as the quality of finished products [15].

In previous studies [15, 18] it was established that the addition of nanomagnetite (NPs $\text{FeO}\times\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3$) to food products leads to a comprehensive improvement of their food, consumer and technological properties. So, in particular, nanoparticles NPs $\text{FeO}\times\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ have bacteriostatic, bactericidal, and antioxidant properties, promotes better digestion of protein components of food, exhibits a moisture-, fat-retaining, and fat-emulsifying effect, is a source of easily digestible iron, and has a beneficial effect on metabolic processes [19].

To determine the degree of development of harmful fungi, a microscopic examination of drugs derived from fungal colonies was performed. Images of the corresponding drugs were obtained by microimaging (**Fig. 3, 4**).

Fig. 3. Micrograph of the drug from sample No. 0 from a colony of fungi ($\times 400$ times magnification)

From the given micrographs it is visible that in the sample which does not contain nanomagnetite (NPs $\text{FeO}\times\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3$) there is an intensive development of microflora. So in a preparation which is made of a colony of fungi, even at rather small increase (400 times) the developed mycelium is visible (**Fig. 3**).

Fig. 4. Micrograph of the drug from sample No. 1 from a colony of fungi ($\times 1000$ times magnification)

3. 2. Determination of the effect of nanomagnetite on the quantitative composition of harmful fungal colonies on flax seeds.

In a sample containing nanomagnetite (NPs $\text{FeO} \times \text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3$) in a relatively small amount (0,1 %, sample No. 1) there is inhibition of microflora development. Only at a magnification of 1000 times in the colonies of fungi can be found small and sluggish fragments of mycelium (**Fig. 4**).

In preparations made from sample No. 3 (content of nanomagnetite – NPs $\text{FeO} \times \text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ 0,2 %) from colonies of fungi externally similar to colonies, even at 1000-fold magnification it was not possible to establish the presence of signs of mycelium.

More informative were the studies of samples conducted by a similar method after five days of exposure. Selected samples were diluted three times for seeding. The appearance of the drugs after five days of incubation is shown in **Fig. 5**.

Fig. 5. Micrograph of the drug from sample No. 1 from a colony of fungi ($\times 1000$ times magnification)

On the photomicrograph of the preparation from the fungi colony of sample No. 2 (**Fig. 6**), weak mycelium without reproductive organs can be observed only at maximum magnification. Colonies of this sample contain a large number of cells that do not show vital activity.

Yeast colonies of sample No. 3 (**Fig. 7**) also contain non-viable cells, and in the fungal colonies of this sample, microscopy did not even reveal signs of the presence of mycelium. It is likely that the fungal colonies counted on the petri dishes were false.

From the obtained data it is seen that the addition of nanomagnetic powder (NPs $\text{FeO} \times \text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3$) significantly inhibits the development of microflora in flax seed samples (**Table 1**).

Fig. 6. Photomicrograph of the preparation from sample No. 2 from the fungi colony (×1000 times magnification)

Fig. 7. Micrograph of the drug from sample No. 3 (×1000 times magnification)

Table 1
Microbiological indicators of samples

Sample	0	1	2	3
The number of harmful fungi in 1 gram of product, Q	45×10^4	37×10^4	220×10^3	65×10^3

The addition of nanomagnetite powder (NPs $\text{FeO} \times \text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3$) has a bacteriostatic effect on harmful fungi in flax seeds (inhibits their development) and the concentration of 0.15 % (sample No. 2) is sufficient to implement this function.

3. 3. Mathematical model of the influence of the composition of nanomagnetite on the growth efficiency of harmful fungi in flax seeds

Analysis of the dependence of the growth of the number of harmful fungi on the composition of nanomagnetite allows to determine the following properties:

1. The general dependence demonstrates a continuous decrease in the number of harmful elements with an increase in nanomagnetite.
2. At the initial stage, with a small amount of magnetite, the bacteriostatic efficiency decreases slightly, which is mathematically proven by the zero value of the derivative.
3. With a significant composition of magnetite, the bacteriostatic efficiency significantly decreases compared to the initial stage and gradually turns into an asymptotic dependence.

A function with a negative exponent whose argument has the form of a power function can correspond to similar properties.

If to determine the number of harmful fungi N , the composition of nanomagnetite, the proposed function can look like this

$$N = N_0 e^{\left(\frac{u}{a}\right)^2}$$

The unknown coefficients of this dependence can be determined by the method of least squares. For our case, the searched dependency looks like this

$$N = 4.5 \cdot 10^5 e^{\left(\frac{u}{0.192}\right)^2}.$$

The graph of this dependence is shown in **Fig. 8**.

The proposed dependence makes it possible to predict the effectiveness of the growth of the number of harmful fungi depending on the content of nanomagnetite and to determine the amount of nanomagnetite necessary to ensure bacteriostatic properties.

Fig. 8. Model of the dependence of the number of harmful fungi on the amount of nanomagnetite

4. Conclusion

The main harmful substances in the storage of flax seeds intended for food use are harmful fungal microorganisms. The use of nanomagnetic powder (NPs $\text{FeO} \times \text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3$) containing of double oxide of ferrous and trivalent iron (NPs $\text{FeO} \times \text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3$) significantly reduces the growth rate of such microorganisms on the seeds of flax. These results allow to recommend the addition of nanoparticles of magnetic powders during storage of flax seeds.

1. The addition of nanomagnetite to flax seeds infected with harmful fungi significantly reduces their ability to grow. The size of harmful fungi is reduced by 3–5 times, with a higher concentration, the size of harmful fungi is reduced by 10–20 times.

2. The number of colonies of harmful fungi decreases by 1.5–2 times, by 8–10 times with the addition of 0.2 % nanomagnetite.

3. The proposed mathematical function allows predicting the number and size of harmful fungi when nanomagnetite is added. The composition of nanomagnetite 0.15 % is sufficient to significantly suppress the development of harmful fungi

4. The proposed methods of protecting flax seeds with the help of nanomagnetite allow to increase significantly their protective properties and significantly slow down their development even at the stage of infection.

5. The conducted research contributes to the expansion of the range of high-quality food products for military personnel with an extended expiry date.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest in relation to this paper, as well as the published research results, including the financial aspects of conducting the research, obtaining and using its results, as well as any non-financial personal relationships.

Funding

The study was performed without financial support.

Data availability

Data will be made available on reasonable request.

References

- [1] Bruno, M. C., Posik, D. M., Zappa, M. E., Baroni, V., Wunderlin, D., Giovambattista, G., García, P. P. (2020). Genetic identification of flax, chia and sesame seeds in processed foods. *Food Control*, 118, 107374. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodcont.2020.107374>
- [2] Brigante, F. I., Lucini Mas, A., Erban, A., Fehrlé, I., Martínez-Seidel, F., Kopka, J. et al. (2022). Authenticity assessment of commercial bakery products with chia, flax and sesame seeds: Application of targeted and untargeted metabolomics results from seeds and lab-scale cookies. *Food Control*, 140, 109114. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodcont.2022.109114>
- [3] Brigante, F. I., Podio, N. S., Wunderlin, D. A., Baroni, M. V. (2022). Comparative metabolite fingerprinting of chia, flax and sesame seeds using LC-MS untargeted metabolomics. *Food Chemistry*, 371, 131355. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2021.131355>
- [4] Rozhmina, T., Samsonova, A., Kanapin, A., Samsonova, M. (2022). An account of Fusarium wilt resistance in flax *Linum usitatissimum*: The disease severity data. *Data in Brief*, 41, 107869. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dib.2022.107869>
- [5] Choudhry, A., Sharma, A., Khan, T. A., Chaudhry, S. A. (2021). Flax seeds based magnetic hybrid nanocomposite: An advance and sustainable material for water cleansing. *Journal of Water Process Engineering*, 42, 102150. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jwpe.2021.102150>
- [6] Farag, S. M., Essa, E. E., Alharbi, S. A., Alfarraj, S., Abu El-Hassan, G. M. M. (2021). Agro-waste derived compounds (flax and black seed peels): Toxicological effect against the West Nile virus vector, *Culex pipiens* L. with special reference to GC-MS analysis. *Saudi Journal of Biological Sciences*, 28 (9), 5261–5267. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sjbs.2021.05.038>
- [7] Gu, S.-Y., Shin, H.-C., Kim, D.-J., Park, S. U., Kim, Y.-K. (2021). The content and health risk assessment of micro and toxic elements in cereals (oat and quinoa), legumes (lentil and chick pea), and seeds (chia, hemp, and flax). *Journal of Food Composition and Analysis*, 99, 103881. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jfca.2021.103881>
- [8] Xie, D., Dai, Z., Yang, Z., Tang, Q., Deng, C., Xu, Y. et al. (2019). Combined genome-wide association analysis and transcriptome sequencing to identify candidate genes for flax seed fatty acid metabolism. *Plant Science*, 286, 98–107. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.plantsci.2019.06.004>
- [9] Karimzadeh Soureshjani, H., Bahador, M., Tadayon, M., Ghorbani Dehkordi, A. (2019). Modelling seed germination and seedling emergence of flax and sesame as affected by temperature, soil bulk density, and sowing depth. *Industrial Crops and Products*, 141, 111770. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.indcrop.2019.111770>
- [10] Bi, J., Song, A., Li, S., Chen, M., Wang, Y., Wang, S., Si, Z. et al. (2022). Plant physiology, microbial community, and risks of multiple fungal diseases along a soil nitrogen gradient. *Applied Soil Ecology*, 175, 104445. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apsoil.2022.104445>
- [11] Asad, S. A. (2022). Mechanisms of action and biocontrol potential of *Trichoderma* against fungal plant diseases - A review. *Ecological Complexity*, 49, 100978. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecocom.2021.100978>
- [12] Pal, G., Kumar, K., Verma, A., Verma, S. K. (2022). Seed inhabiting bacterial endophytes of maize promote seedling establishment and provide protection against fungal disease. *Microbiological Research*, 255, 126926. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.micres.2021.126926>
- [13] Singh, P., Chatterjee, A., Rajput, L. S., Rana, S., Kumar, S., Nataraj, V. et al. (2021). Development of an intelligent laser biospeckle system for early detection and classification of soybean seeds infected with seed-borne fungal pathogen (*Colletotrichum truncatum*). *Biosystems Engineering*, 212, 442–457. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biosystemseng.2021.11.002>
- [14] Fursik, O., Strashynskiy, I., Pasichniy, V., Marynin, A. (2019). Some aspects of using the nanotechnology in food industry. *Ukrainian Journal of Food Science*, 7 (2), 298–306. doi: <https://doi.org/10.24263/2310-1008-2019-7-2-12>
- [15] Tsykhanovska, I., Evlash, V., Lazarieva, T., Aleksandrov, O., Blahyi, O., Gontar, T., Bykanova, K. (2021). Functional and technological properties of food nanoadditive based on double oxide of ferrous and trivalent iron in production molded jelly marmalade. *Ukrainian Journal of Food Science*, 9(1), 115–125. doi: <https://doi.org/10.24263/2310-1008-2021-9-1-11>
- [16] Chow, Y. Y., Ting, A. S. Y. (2019). Influence of fungal infection on plant tissues: FTIR detects compositional changes to plant cell walls. *Fungal Ecology*, 37, 38–47. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.funeco.2018.10.004>
- [17] te Giffel, M. C., Zwietering, M. H. (1999). Validation of predictive models describing the growth of *Listeria monocytogenes*. *International Journal of Food Microbiology*, 46 (2), 135–149. doi: [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0168-1605\(98\)00189-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0168-1605(98)00189-5)
- [18] Tsykhanovska, I., Evlash, V., Aleksandrov, O., Tovma, L. (2020). Functional and technological properties of food nanoadditives based on double oxide of divalent and trivalent iron. *Ukrainian Journal of Food Science*, 8 (1), 36–48. doi: <https://doi.org/10.24263/2310-1008-2020-8-1-5>
- [19] Riabchykov, M., Alexandrov, A., Trishch, R., Nikulina, A., Korolyova, N. (2022). Prospects for the Development of Smart Clothing with the Use of Textile Materials with Magnetic Properties. *Tekstilec*, 65 (1), 36–43. doi: <https://doi.org/10.14502/tekstilec.65.2021050>